

Chemical Examination of *Abroma augusta*

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The plant, *Abroma augusta* Linn. f. (Fam : Sterculiaceae) which grows throughout India, is reported^{1,2} to be useful in dysmenorrhoea and as an uterine tonic. As the presence of alkaloids and steroids in the root of this plant was reported earlier^{3,4}, and the leaves have not been chemically investigated, we thought it desirable to investigate the same. We here report the isolation of taraxeryl acetate, taraxerol, β -sitosterol and a low melting neutral compound from the petroleum ether extract of the leaves of *Abroma augusta*.

Air dried powdered leaves (0.6 kg.) of *Abroma augusta* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for 18 hr., the product concentrated (15 g.) and chromatographed over a column of Brockmann alumina. Elution with petroleum ether afforded a reddish oily product (Compound A). Further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) and with solvents of increasing polarities yielded two other semi solid products (Compounds B and C) respectively.

Compound A was rechromatographed over a column of silica gel. The petroleum ether eluates furnished a crystalline solid, which responded to positive Libermann Burchardt colour reaction for triterpenes and analysed for the molecular formula $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 295–97°, $[\alpha]_D + 12.8^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). It gave a yellow colour with tetranitromethane indicating the presence of unsaturation. The presence of an acetate function was evident from the appearance of peaks at 5.80 μ (acetate CO) and 8.02 μ (O–COCH₃) in the i.r. spectrum (nujol). It was characterised as taraxeryl acetate by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., t.l.c., rotation and i.r.) with an authentic sample.

Compound B was rechromatographed over silica gel and on elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) yielded two solids. The one, eluted earlier, crystallised from ether, m.p. 84°, and showed no colouration with Libermann Burchardt and tetranitromethane reagents and was not further characterised. The other solid, crystallising from acetone as glistening flakes, m.p. 274–76°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0$ ($CHCl_3$) gave a pink colour in Libermann Burchardt test for triterpene and analysed for $C_{30}H_{50}O$. The compound exhibited a peak at 3.0 μ for –OH group in its i.r. spectrum (nujol). The triterpene alcohol furnished an acetate, m.p. 297–98°, showing new peaks at 5.81 and 8.02 μ , for acetoxy group and absence of the –OH peak at 3.0 μ in its i.r. spectrum. The above data suggest its identity with taraxerol and this has been confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., i.r. and t.l.c.) with an authentic sample.

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Compound C, on rechromatography over a column of Brockmann alumina and elution with benzene yielded shining needles, m.p. 137–38° on crystallisation from methanol-acetone mixture. It showed positive Libermann Burchardt test for sterols and could be characterised as β -sitosterol by direct comparison with an authentic specimen (m.m.p. and i.r.). The latter formed an acetate, m.p. 127–28° which showed no depression in its melting point upon admixture with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol acetate.

We are currently investigating the alcoholic extract of the leaves of this plant in search of other constituents.

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